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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of
Work Report

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aim/Objectives of Report

The report is developed in the frames of the INGAME project (Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation - A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy) funded by the EU and represents one of the specific deliverables of Work Package 2 (Mapping the INGAME Ecosystem of Needs, Practices Target Groups, Stakeholders and Mode of Work).

The research conducted for WP2 aims to identify existing good practices and, where possible, to reinforce them. Research also aim towards identifying gaps and issues in existing practices - in particular, the difficulty of involving young people (18-35) in issues of civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality.

2. Key findings from Desk Research

Desk-based research involves the analysis of recent, relevant and available data and resources (literature, reports, policy documents, previous surveys, research studies, etc.) on the pedagogical models for fostering awareness on issues related to social inclusion, gender equality and civic participation for youth developing intercultural skills and positive attitudes with the use of games in both formal and informal learning environments for youth.

Researchers also pay attention to “good practices” that uses online gaming to raise youth awareness on social inclusion, gender equality and civic participation.

2.1. Literature Review/National Context

Civic engagement

As described by Berlin political scientist Herfried Münkler, in the case of civil society it is 'a body that compensates for the effects of market and state dynamics', which complements the principle of legalism and political power in the sphere of the state and maximizes the benefits in the sphere of the economy by means of morality and oriented towards the well-being of citizens in general, which cannot be 'created by the state by means of coercive measures or be implemented by a competitive economy'.

The development of civil society is stimulated by two forces; on the one hand, an external force, which is the intensity of political and market change, and on the other hand the internal side, which is the ethical attitude of those who want to contribute its contribution to good social life, with attention and recognition as additional drivers.

One of the three basic objectives of the transformation in Poland in general, as in other countries of Central and Eastern Europe after 1989, was, in addition to introducing a system of freedom, democracy and the state the law and the market economy to create a functioning civil society.

Social capital, which in Robert Putnam's understanding refers to social networks and related standards, reaches less than 20 percent in Poland. It is one of the lowest indicators in Europe. Poland also has one of the lowest levels of civil society participation. Such a relatively rare involvement in this area is a result of the cultural depreciation of society during the communist era.

In terms of content, most NGOs (almost 40%) are active in the sphere of spending free time, less than 23% in the cultural sphere, about 10% in education and upbringing and in the social sphere and 6% in the regional development sector. Only 1.8% of NGOs are involved in political affairs and human rights.

The biggest obstacle to building civil society is the poor financial situation. The main sources of funding, in addition to voluntary contributions, are public funds, accounting for almost 36%. The share of public funds to support civil society is two or even three times lower than in Western European countries.

According to conservative estimates, the Polish NGO sector is at least three times weaker in economic terms than the average in Western countries.

In this context, foreign capital and EU funds play a significant role, and in 2008, according to their own declarations, only 9 percent of organizations used them of non-governmental organizations, currently it is up to 65 percent, which in the end is not a small proportion of the funding the sphere of civil society. In addition to the financial aspect, EU assistance also covers organizational, cultural and political aspects.

Currently in Poland we are dealing with a "historical transformation of civil society into a "political society",

breaking with the apolitical paradigm of civil action'? I think we should talk about at least three phenomena that are to some extent interrelated, but not identical:

- 1) a reorientation of part of the third sector towards greater involvement in current policies,

2) the growing political involvement of the public, including people who have not yet been involved in such activities; and

3) attempts to enter into institutional policy taken by activists and activists, especially urban movements.

Each of these trends results primarily from disappointment with institutional policy and the search for new solutions. The politicization of NGOs is manifested by among other things, in greater involvement than hitherto in debates on the systemic reforms introduced, in open criticism of governments and seeking support in international institutions.

Social inclusion

According to a survey conducted by CBOS in 2019, 81% of respondents declared voluntary and unpaid pro-social activity, of which more than half (54%) indicated their share only in the non-institutionalized area, more than a quarter (26%) combined individual activity with work in organizations, and only a few (1%) declared activity for the sole benefit of the institution.

Out of 68% of adult Poles did not engage in activities of any social group of a civic nature (17% declared that they devoted their attention to one such organization, 7% to two and 8% to three or more). It is also worth emphasizing that more often than others, respondents aged 35-44 (40%) and 18-24 (39%) declared active membership in civic organizations, and Pupils and students- 36% (and also: middle level employees- 48%, people with higher education- 47%, respondents with the highest monthly income per capita- 39%, satisfied with their own material situation- 38%, as well as private entrepreneurs- 38%).

The youngest The respondents (18-24 years of age), including mainly pupils and students, are distinguished by The number of people who are active in sports associations, clubs and associations (14%), as well as youth organizations such as scouting, student or student clubs and associations (9%) and in artistic groups such as the Boy Scouts, the Students' Clubs and Associations (9%). choir, dance or theatre group (7%)".

Gender equality

Eurostat reports that the gender pay gap in Poland is relatively low at 7.2%. Thus, Poland is among the five European Union countries with the lowest wage gap.

However, less optimistic information is provided by the Central Statistical Office (GUS), which carried out the survey in 2016 and its results indicate that the difference in wages between women and men is 18.5%.

The state of such things, according to the EC, results from a phenomenon called the "glass ceiling". It says that at a certain point in women's careers it is more difficult or almost impossible for them to get promoted¹.

The Constitution of the Republic of Poland (the most important legal act in Poland) in Article 33- "Principle of equality between women and men"². This article says that both men and women have „(...)equal rights in family, political, social and economic life in the Republic of Poland³” and that they have „(...) equal rights, in particular, regarding education, employment and promotion, and shall have the right to equal compensation for work of similar value, to social security, to hold offices, and to receive public honours and decorations⁴”.

Besides the Constitution, the provisions governing equality can also be found in The Polish Labour Code.

Art. 11² „Principle of equality of employees. Employees have equal rights in respect of the same performance of the same duties; this applies in particular to the equal treatment of men and women in employment⁵”

Art. 11³ „Prohibition against discrimination in employment. Any discrimination in employment, direct or indirect, in particular in respect of gender, age, disability, race, religion, nationality, political views, trade union membership, ethnic origin, creed, sexual orientation or in respect of the conditions of employment for a definite or an indefinite period of time or full or part time, are prohibited.⁶”

Important facts:

- There are currently 131 female members of the Polish Parliament (out of a total of 460), which is less than 28.5%. In Poland, the gender is not equally represented in this field.

¹ A. Bartosiewicz, *Tylko jedno stanowisko kierownicze na trzy zajmuje kobieta. Porównaj różnice w zarobkach obu płci*, Available on: <https://strefabiznesu.pl/tylko-jedno-stanowisko-kierownicze-na-trzy-zajmuje-kobieta-porownaj-roznice-w-zarobkach-obu-plci/ar/c10-14554023>.

² Dz.U.1997.78.483 - The Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 2nd April, 1997.

³ *ibid.*

⁴ *ibid.*

⁵ Art. 11 § 2 ustawy z dnia 26 czerwca 1974 r. Kodeks Pracy (Dz.U.2019.0.1040), [en: Article 11 § 2 of the Labour Code Act of 26 June 1974 (Journal of Laws 2019.0.1040)].

⁶ Art. 11 § 3 ustawy z dnia 26 czerwca 1974 r. Kodeks Pracy (Dz.U.2019.0.1040), [en: Article 11 § 3 of the Labour Code Act of 26 June 1974 (Journal of Laws 2019.0.1040)].

- The OECD report "Entrepreneurship at a Glance 2017" indicates that there are 1,471 thousand self-employed men and 731 thousand self-employed women in Poland (data for 2016 or the nearest known date). This shows that self-employment is still the domain of men in Poland.
- Based on the available data, the ratio of women to men is low when it comes to self-employment. Although the law in Poland ensures equality to employment, it is still men who are more likely to choose this option. It is no better on the political front. Here, too, the vast majority are men, which is often dictated by the party situation and the presence of women on the electoral "one". There are also differences in salaries and promotion opportunities, and here, depending on the source, we get different data. Based on Eurostat calculations, the gap exists, but it is not as large, but the Central Statistical Office's data already inform us about a large pay gap.
- Women may encounter various barriers during their professional life. These may include stereotypes, difficulties in relations with superiors or different treatment in the case of promotion opportunities. Some of the barriers, however, can be found in the women themselves. These are usually psychological barriers such as low self-esteem or fear of social rejection. Another barrier may be on the line between self-employment and family. Here, there may be situations where the family is sceptical about a woman giving up a permanent job and stability in favour of risk and creating her own company. Another barrier is the poor care infrastructure. The problem occurring mainly in small towns and villages in Poland.

Social inclusion

Social Inclusion of Youth in Poland

The scale of social exclusion of young people in Poland against the background of EU member states places Poland in an average position. In 2018, in the majority of EU Member States the social exclusion rate for young people (aged 16-29) was lower for those living with their parents than for those who were not, but Poland was an exception.

A significant proportion of the population at risk of exclusion in Poland lives in marginalized and poor regions, which hinders them from exercising their fundamental rights and threatens their future. In the activation activities undertaken, it is necessary to take into account the local context and individualization of activities (taking into account the expectations and capabilities of the individual). Moreover, social inclusion of youth in Poland is observed to be quite often acquainted with the exclusion of persons with disabilities in their equal participation in activities with other representatives of the group of youth. Disabilities remain a taboo, and persons with different types of

disabilities themselves feel that they do not belong to the same community as their peers. Although more youth with disabilities see the need to "get out" of this kind of exclusion, eliminate barriers, developing skills in anticipating threats, the person is not able to overcome these difficulties themselves.

At the education level, to support such youth demonstrating different types of exclusion, from September 1, 2011, gradually, step by step, year after year, Polish schools and other educational institutions started entering a new model for providing and organizing psychological and pedagogical assistance to pupils and students, their parents and teachers (MEN 2010).

Together with Poland's accession to the European Union, new policies for the inclusion of the youth were introduced at national level:

The State Strategy for Youth for 2003-2012 (based on the work of the EC, with the aim to create the right conditions for young people aged 15 to 25 to enable them to participate in social, cultural and political life on an equal footing with other social groups). In 2005 the Strategy was recognised as a core document in the field of youth policy as a result of the Government's Position on the implementation of the European Youth Pact. However, in 2009 due to public discourse the policy stopped being treated as a document that organises activities related to youth issues.

Joint Memorandum for Social Integration and National Action Plan for Social Integration 2004-2006. In 2005-2010, specific actions taken to prevent social exclusion of youth were regulated and outlined by the National Strategy for Social Integration adopted for 2005-2010.

Current documents on the existence of national strategy on social inclusion:

The National Programme for Combating Poverty and Social Exclusion 2020. A New Dimension of Active Inclusion (including the Operational Objective to create opportunities for young people to enter the labour market and start a family, for a better future). – part of the Long-Term National Development Strategy- Poland 2030.

The Programme: Active Forms of Combating Social Exclusion – A New Dimension 2020 (including the Specific Objective to integrate young people, particularly from communities at risk of social exclusion, into the local environment through education and integrative activities).

The use of EU funds has also been supporting the implementation of activities for the social inclusion of the youth, targeted to different disadvantages of this specific group. There are also more and more strategies implemented at regional level taking into account factors and processes that can support the minimization of social problems affecting different social groups.

However, there is a need for even greater involvement of local governments, inter-sectoral cooperation of local institutions and organizations for the social and professional reintegration of

young people. There is also a need for further in-depth research in the area of youth social exclusion. The main research direction should concern the regional specificity of social exclusion, including the causes and consequences, its dynamics, range and areas implying the special need to counteract social exclusion of young people.

Usability of online games in informal educational environments and their impact in addressing the above-mentioned topics.

In Poland, the term gamification came into use in 2012, mentioned in the book by P. Tkaczyk "Grywalizacja" [J. Woźniak 2015, p. 95].

A novelty is the implementation of educational games- not the essence of the phenomenon itself. Gamification was recognized as one of the greatest discoveries of management, now it is increasingly used to build relationships with the client [A. Widawska- Stanisz 2017, p. 8]

Some time ago games were introduced in early childhood education. In higher education, gamification is being used at some universities where applied is the e-learning method.

Various online findings show that for the best results it is essential to provide social recognition and rewards in educational games. Gaps are recognized in measuring the efficiency of introducing gamification to education.

According to research entitled 'Gamification in academic education – possibilities and limitations of its utilization in the student's education' carried out in 2016 at the University of Rzeszow it was found that gamification can be a valuable method of building student involvement in the process of their education. Students demonstrate a positive attitude towards using gamification in academic education.

2.2. Good Practices

The use of gamification in Poland is becoming increasingly popular. There are many projects that use the game for education and are good practices. Some of them are described below:

- EntrInno – EntrInno is a project funded by the European Commission for addressing the need for optimizing the development of entrepreneurship and innovation in Europe. Its main focus is to enhance the skills of young EU citizens, a crucial population of a progressive, entrepreneurial and market-based economy and society. For that purpose, an interactive online game was developed, which is accessible online and offline, and can be adapted to fit various contexts. This game serving the development of entrepreneurial and leadership skills as well as innovation, creativity and cooperation.

EntrInno project was addressed to young adults (aged 18 – 35). In effect of project implementation, an educational on-line game had been created. At the beginning, the partners had conducted research about existing pedagogical models for fostering entrepreneurial and innovation skills, about training needs of young people as well as evaluation of existing games in the field of promoting entrepreneurial and innovation skills. The state of art report was created which served as the basis for the game. The game was made available via computers and mobile devices.

More information: <http://www.entrinno.org/>

- Gamify Your Teaching – increasing vocational competences of entrepreneurship Teachers with the use of gamification. The main objective of the project is to support the professional development and competence of teachers and trainers of entrepreneurship and the emphasis on teaching ICT through the use of innovative tools and approaches to teaching using gamification. Within the project a simulation game with practical elements was created, which covered 7 thematic areas in the field of entrepreneurship and the methodology of teaching entrepreneurship through gamification.

More information: <http://gamify-project.eu/>

- Spaceu2019 is an online tool for the European Parliament elections in 2019. It is designed for mobile EU citizens who vote in their country of citizenship or residence. The tool is an interactive database that informs about their electoral rights. It allows to compare the conditions and requirements for participation in the political process. The second part of the tool is euandi2019. It is an application that allows citizens to find the political party that best suits their views.

The main objective of Spaceu2019 is to create informed and active citizenship throughout Europe and getting citizens to vote. The main target group is mobile EU citizens, people with dual citizenship, and other EU citizens. The tool is accessible to all and provides citizens with useful information on how to vote and which parties are best suited to them.

More information: <http://spaceu2019.eu/>

- Equality in business program - the project's activities focus on developing solutions for medium-sized enterprises that can turn a company into a place that is friendly and attractive for current and new employees.

The offer of the programme includes:

- Training to acquire knowledge of legal provisions related to equal treatment in the workplace,
- Business advice- individual support
- E-learning training- education of employees on equal treatment in the workplace
- Tools such as educational films, equality training programmes, etc.
- Competition promoting companies that apply solutions for equal opportunities for women and men in the labour market

More information: <https://cofund.org.pl/projekty/rownosc-szans-w-biznesie----praktyczne-narzedzie-realizacji-zasady-rownosci-szans-kobiet-i-mezczyzn->

- Social Integration Programme implemented under the Post-accession Rural Development Programme. The main objective of the programme is to increase social integration of the inhabitants of communes from rural areas. The programme is implemented by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy from the funds of the World Bank.

Strategic objectives:

- Creation of a catalogue of good practices
- Dissemination of good practices among local governments
- Implementation of inclusive social assistance services to support older people, children and young people and families
- Acquiring strategic planning skills in solving social problems
- Development of municipal strategies for solving social problems
- Training and expert support in developing and updating strategies and providing social services

More information: <https://www.annopol.info/urząd/wazne-dokumenty/program-integracji-spoecznej.html#>

- The Powerplay game is a didactic package that includes a strategy game, an online guide and materials for teachers. The main goal of the game is to introduce the concept of entrepreneurship developed in accordance with the principles of sustainable development among 12-15 year old, to improve key competences and skills that are relevant to the labour market, to increase creativity and innovation in school education and to improve educational achievements of young people.

The game consists of a board, action cards, company profiles and other materials useful for playing and teaching the game.

More information: <http://powerplayer.info/pl/strona-glowna/>

- ACTIVE lessons And gamification for better social inclusion- This project is aimed at young people and its main objective is to exchange experiences of interactive classroom activities, to improve the quality of education and to involve students in participation. The main themes of the project are social inclusion, diversity and peer learning. The project uses different didactic methods such as gamification, peer learning, active lessons, street games and art activities.

More information: <https://www.erasmusactivate.com/>

- Gamification – Innovative Solutions for Social Issues- A 7-day training course for youth workers and youth leaders from the partner countries (Poland, Croatia, Romania, Bulgaria, Italy, Malta, Lithuania, UK and Czech Republic). It aims at developing operational skills by learning innovative methods of social activation of youth. The project explores the phenomenon of gamification as a method aimed at involving young people in solving problems of their local communities. Social engagement aims at empowering young people in their local communities and preventing social and economic exclusion.

During the project, people working with young people discussed how to involve young people in activities for the benefit of their communities, discussed good practices and learned about gamification principles. The project initiated a network of organisations using gamification in youth work (also through the creation of "IDEA-KIT"), able to support each other and replicate good practices in different social contexts in Europe.

More information: <https://cetplatform.org/gamification/>

Poland runs and participates in many programmes and projects aimed at encouraging entrepreneurship among women. Among them we can distinguish, for example:

- Schemat małych grantów dla przedsiębiorczych kobiet [eng: Small grants scheme for enterprising women] – This programme supports women's activities through financial support of up to EUR 200 000. Among the requirements is that women applying for a grant should be active in one of three areas: technology and environmental innovation and improving quality of life⁷.
- Aktywna i niezależna – program wsparcia przedsiębiorczości kobiet [eng: Active and independent- a programme to support female entrepreneurship] – The project aim was to support women from the Pomorskie Voivodeship by providing a grant to start a business (PLN 24 000), but also offered substantive support in the field of consulting or training.⁸

There are currently not many projects at national level promoting gender equality in Poland. However, there are principles such as, for example, the 'principle of equal opportunities for women and men', which aim to ensure that all implemented projects are created with respect for both genders. There was more activity in previous years in this type of social projects. Currently, although of course such projects are still being implemented at different administrative levels, new topics and problems are emerging. As far as women are concerned, there is an increasing number of projects aimed at encouraging them to take up technical studies and study science profiles.

⁷ <https://www.parp.gov.pl/component/grants/grants/technologie-dla-kobiet>

⁸ <https://grupaprofesja.com/projekty/aktywna-i-niezalezna-program-wsparcia-przedsiębiorczości-kobiet/>

3. Research results: questionnaires

3.1. Research sample

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, we were unable to conduct physical meetings with our target group. The consortium decided that we will conduct online research using Google forms. We created 3 questionnaires in which the target groups could answer questions about civic participation and gamification. All responses were anonymous, used exclusively for the INGAME project.

The aim of the questionnaires was to find out what respondents think about civic participation of young people and how it can be increased. The first questionnaire was distributed to young people aged 18-35 years. Three women and two men of different age groups took part in the survey (see graph). All participants in the survey were involved in work-related activities. Four of them were engaged in work, while only one was a student.

What is your age?

5 odpowiedzi

Graph 1 Q1 age group of respondents

The second questionnaire was directed to 5 stakeholders in a different age group (see graph 2). Four women and one man took part in this survey. Three of them were aged 36-45, and two of them 26-35. As shown below, two of the respondents work in youth training institutions, one in Youth organization, one in Civil Society Organization and one in Public Institution and Social Services (graph

3)

What is your age?

5 odpowiedzi

What is the type of your organization? Please select from below.

5 odpowiedzi

Graph 2 & 3 Stakeholders demographics & sector

The last, third questionnaire was directed to 30 target group members (18-35 years). 31 people took part in the survey, 14 of them were men and 17 women. As we can see in the chart below, 35.5% were aged 21-25, 35.5% were aged 26-30, 16.1% were aged 31-35 and 12.9% were aged 18-20.

What is your age?

31 odpowiedzi

Graph 4 Target group respondents age group

Most of the respondents (80,6%) were currently engaged in a study or work activity, the graph below shows the study or work activity they were currently engaged in.

If yes, which one?

26 odpowiedzi

Graph 8 participants' engagement

3.2. Needs analysis

The research conducted under the INGAME project shows that most of the respondents are involved in social life and actively participate in the local community. When asked what civic engagement means to them, answers were often provided such as being active in local community, participation in the elections, volunteering etc. (for more details, see Evaluation Grids). Most of the respondents admitted to having participated in initiatives such as Flashmob, Awareness campaigns on social networks, Petition, Square demonstrations, marches, sit-in, which shows that young people want to be active in social life.

Research shows that both young people (target group) and stakeholders consider civic engagement to be very important and that more initiatives and information are needed for young people to become more involved and to encourage their active participation in society. Most of the respondents are familiar with new technologies and believe that this is a very important element that will help young people in their civic engagement. New technologies are part of our daily life. We use phones and tablets on a daily basis, which are our source of information to learn and increase our knowledge on various topics. Through new technologies we get more information and can communicate with

others to express our opinions, organize various social activities and create a local community. They believe that through technology we have more opportunities.

The survey participants reacted very positively to the creation of an online game in terms of civic engagement. They think it is a very good idea that will help young people to get interested in this topic. Gamification solutions must be supported by clear instructions for users to understand how to proceed and what is their aim. They believe that such a game should be easily accessible, have good graphics and interesting content. One of the suggestion is that such game should have feature realistic scenarios and should be available through different devices, not only PC, but mobile devices and should include good practices – some practical examples, also it would be great if there will be a possibility to connect with other users.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Key results of research (short summary)

Social inclusion, civic engagement and gender equality are becoming increasingly important in modern society.

The research shows that most young people are involved in various social activities such as volunteering, and they also acknowledge that the use of technology today is a great opportunity to promote such initiatives. They allow us to communicate with others and create a virtual community.

In Poland, there are programmes that promote various activities supporting gender equality or social inclusion, it is important to promote such activities using various innovative technologies.

There are many games and platforms that can increase our knowledge. Not everyone knew exactly what the game-based learning initiatives are, but some respondents gave some examples such as: Duolingo, Stratagame, Ruby Warrior, Codin Game, Kahoot, Quizzes, Score Hunter etc. They believe that games allow us to learn through play, so that we can acquire knowledge faster and learn with pleasure.

4.2. Recommendations for future action

Using game – based approaches for promoting gender equality, social inclusion and civic engagement has many benefits and surpasses other forms of teaching.

Educational games teach how to use the acquired knowledge and enable to gain experience in the virtual world, which can later shape patterns of behaviour and directly influence the students' reactions. People are encouraged to use knowledge from different fields to choose the right solution or make a decision. They can also see how the outcome of the game changes with their actions and decisions. Students can contact other team members and discuss with each other, thus improving their interpersonal skills.

Playing enhances the ability to innovate and adapt to changing conditions and is an active process of continuously shaping views on how the world works.

5. References

Bartosiewicz, Tylko jedno stanowisko kierownicze na trzy zajmuje kobieta. Porównaj różnice w zarobkach obu płci, Available on: <https://strefabiznesu.pl/tylko-jedno-stanowisko-kierownicze-na-trzy-zajmuje-kobieta-porownaj-roznice-w-zarobkach-obu-plci/ar/c10-14554023>.

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<https://www.parp.gov.pl/component/grants/grants/technologie-dla-kobiet>

<https://grupaprofesja.com/projekty/aktywna-i-niezalezna-program-wsparcia-przedsiębiorczosci-kobiet/>

https://www.depot.ceon.pl/bitstream/handle/123456789/12827/Wykluczenie_społeczne_1p.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y

http://www.owes.info.pl/biblioteka/wyklad_wykluczenie_społeczne.pdf

<https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/en/content/youthwiki/43-strategy-social-inclusion-young-people-poland>

6. Annexes

6.1. Annex 1: Questionnaire 1 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 1 (target group)																
Partner																
Age profile of the participants <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	<p>18-20: 1 21-25: 1</p> <p>26-30: 2 31-35: 1</p> <p>What is your age? 5 odpowiedzi</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Age Distribution Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Age Group</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>18-20 years</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>21-25 years</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>26-30 years</td> <td>2</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>31-35 years</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Age Group	Count	Percentage	18-20 years	1	20%	21-25 years	1	20%	26-30 years	2	40%	31-35 years	1	20%
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26-30 years	2	40%														
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Number of participants and their gender split	<p><i>Females: 2 Males: 3</i></p> <p>What is you gender? 5 odpowiedzi</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Gender Distribution Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Female</td> <td>2</td> <td>60%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Male</td> <td>3</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Gender	Count	Percentage	Female	2	60%	Male	3	40%						
Gender	Count	Percentage														
Female	2	60%														
Male	3	40%														

In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:

Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
<p>1. What does social involvement mean to you?</p>	<p>The respondents were asked what civic engagement means to them. The respondents were unanimous and mentioned mainly involvement in the local community, responsibility, expressing one's own opinion, participation in elections, and participation in activities in public space, manifested also in an interest of what is happening around us.</p>	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>

<p>2.</p> <p>What activities do you think should be offered to increase young people's participation in public life and - more specifically - their social involvement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - promoting civic engagement in social media, using innovative tools, games, videos - debates with other young people, in which you can exchange your views on the subject. Social actions to increase civic awareness, volunteering, social spot - information videos - Young adults should be educated about their possibilities, what can they do and how their actions can impact the country. There should also be more promotion of this topic. - Introducing the matter through educational institutions, when at University or while other levels of learning. - Debates, workshops 	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>
<p>3.</p> <p>Do you know any policies, practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality? If so, should they improve or change?</p>	<p>Most of the respondents heard about programmes that promote gender equality and also met with school debates and days of self-government that promote civic engagement.</p>	<p>Some of the respondents have never heard of any policies, practices and interventions for promoting young civic engagement, social inclusion and gender equality. They believe that such actions are needed and should be presented in an innovative way to encourage young people</p>
<p>4.</p> <p>Are you aware of new technologies</p>	<p>4 out of 5 respondents admitted that they are aware of new technologies but most of them never had a</p>	<p>One of the respondents has never heard of new technologies and innovative approaches.</p>

<p>(digital and mobile resources such as GPS, PDAs, Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (such as Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning)...</p>	<p>chance to use them. One person gave Ms Monopoly's game as an example of game-based learning, which is designed to empower women.</p>	<p>The respondents also did not know of any online game that promotes civic engagement, but they find this approach very interesting.</p>
<p>5. We are developing an online game, INGAME, that enables users to learn from simulated experiences, broaden critical reflection on social and political conditions, build (social) skills and stimulate interest in collective action. What does an online game like INGAME need to arouse your</p>	<p>The data collected from this question shows that the respondents reacted very positively to the online game to be developed under the INGAME project. They gave some important things that game developers should pay attention to when creating the game:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The game should have good graphics and storyline. It would be good if each player had their own character that can improve - this will motivate the players to the best possible result. There should be a variety of interesting things that will be interesting and not long - so as not to bore the player. Ranking of the players is also a good idea to arouse competition. 	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>

<p>interest? What features or characteristics should such a game have?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- should be based on real life-situations and real-life problems that someone can face.- The game should be easily accessible, have good graphics, interesting content. It shouldn't be too easy, but it shouldn't be too hard not to discourage players.- Accessibility through different devices, not only PC, but mobile devices; maybe good practices - practical examples; possibility to connect with other users.- The game should offer the possibility for users to learn by doing. Maybe feature realistic scenarios? A good idea would be to reward users for doing (correct) actions, which will create a sense of achievement. A good game might teach the users or at least pique their interest in the topic and increase their involvement.	
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6.2. Annex 2: Questionnaire 2 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 2 (stakeholders)																										
Partner																										
Age profile of the participants (please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)	<p>36-45: 3 26-35: 2</p> <p>What is your age? 5 odpowiedzi</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Age Profile Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Age Group</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>19-25 years</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>26-35 years</td> <td>2</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>36-45 years</td> <td>3</td> <td>60%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>46-55 years</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Above 55 years</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Age Group	Count	Percentage	19-25 years	0	0%	26-35 years	2	40%	36-45 years	3	60%	46-55 years	0	0%	Above 55 years	0	0%						
Age Group	Count	Percentage																								
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46-55 years	0	0%																								
Above 55 years	0	0%																								
Number of participants and their gender split	<p><i>Females: 4</i> <i>Males: 1</i></p> <p>What is your gender? 5 odpowiedzi</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Gender Split Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Gender</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Female</td> <td>4</td> <td>80%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Male</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Gender	Count	Percentage	Female	4	80%	Male	1	20%															
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Type of organization	<p>What is the type of your organization? Please select from below. 5 odpowiedzi</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Type of Organization Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Organization Type</th> <th>Count</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Youth training institutions</td> <td>2</td> <td>40%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>International Organizations</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Youth Organizations</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Civil Society Organizations</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Public Institutions and Social Services</td> <td>1</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Local Authorities</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Other (please specify)</td> <td>0</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Organization Type	Count	Percentage	Youth training institutions	2	40%	International Organizations	0	0%	Youth Organizations	1	20%	Civil Society Organizations	1	20%	Public Institutions and Social Services	1	20%	Local Authorities	0	0%	Other (please specify)	0	0%
Organization Type	Count	Percentage																								
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In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:																										
Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings																								

<p>1. Which factors influence the civic engagement of young adult?</p>	<p>The respondents agreed that there are many factors that influence the civic engagement of young people. Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reciprocity and equivalence in the pursuit of democratic participation in the rule of law, in full respect of human rights and cultural and environmental diversity - Volunteering - Access to public information - Promotion of correct relations between public authorities and citizens - Workshops - Civic education - Active participation in social and political life - Strengthening family functions and sense of community - Civic awareness-raising initiatives 	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>
<p>2. What kind of activities do you think should be delivered to increase the participation of young adult in public life in general and more specifically, their civic engagement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of social commitment and solidarity - Promotion of civic education in schools - Creating innovative tools - Public debates - Workshops - Organizing civic awareness-raising initiatives - Promotion of projects, that increasing and promoting civic engagement <p>The respondents agreed that all activities should be presented in an innovative way to encourage young people</p>	<p>There are no contrasting findings within the responses.</p>
<p>3. What are the main difficulties you face in involving young people</p>	<p>Most of the respondents notice that young people do not have time to be socially active, think that this is not a topic worthy of attention and prefer to do other</p>	<p>The respondents also admit that young people do not trust public institutions and politicians, which discourages them from social activities.</p>

<p>in civic engagement activities</p>	<p>things during this time. They are focused on achieving their own goals and do not worry about the welfare of the whole community.</p>	
<p>4. In your area of work, do you know of successful initiatives aimed to improve civic participation of young people and their attention to social inclusion or gender equality issues? If so, which are the main elements of success?</p>	<p>Examples of initiatives that were given by the respondents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - „Szlachetna Paczka” - a social project in Poland combining know-how and modern technologies. It creates systemic solutions thanks to which volunteers help those in need - „Młodzi głosują” - involves mobilising informed participation in elections, encouraging young people to take an interest in current socio-political issues - „Żonkile” – social and educational campaign, that commemorates the Warsaw Ghetto Uprising <p>Respondents also give as an example of various types of workshops and volunteer work.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>5. Are you aware of new technologies (digital tools and mobile devices like GPS, PDAs,</p>	<p>Everybody who took part in the survey heard about new technologies, online games, quizzes, which are based on the game. They think this is a very</p>	<p>One of the respondents admitted that he had heard about the concept, but never had a chance to use it.</p>

<p>Tablet PCs, Virtual Reality, hand-held technologies, mobile learning technologies, etc.) and innovative approaches (like for example Online Gaming, Serious Games, Game-based Learning) that can be used to discuss global issues, like social inclusion and gender equality? If yes, have you ever used them and why?</p>	<p>good approach that allows for quick learning.</p>	
<p>We are developing an online game, called INGAME which will allow users to learn from simulated experience enhancing critical reflection on social and political circumstances, build skills and stimulate interest for collective action. What would an online game like INGAME need to attract your interest? Which features would you like the game to have?</p>	<p>Respondents believe that such a game could be more interesting if it motivates players by collecting points and is innovative and accessible to all, without any limitations. It should build social awareness and encourage players to participate in the community.</p>	<p>One of the respondents said that apart from obvious factors such as innovation or motivation, the game should have very good graphics to be attractive for the player.</p>

6.3. Annex 3: Questionnaire 3 – Evaluation Grid

Evaluation grid: questionnaire 3 (target group)	
Partner	
Age profile of the participants <i>(please insert the number of people belonging to each age / age group)</i>	<p>18-20: 4 21-25: 11</p> <p>26-30: 11 31-35: 5</p> <p>What is your age? 31 odpowiedzi</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 18-20 years ● 21-25 years ● 26-30 years ● 31-35 years
Number of participants and their gender split	<p><i>Females: 17</i> <i>Males: 14</i></p> <p>What is you gender? 31 odpowiedzi</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Female ● Male

In minimum 2 pages and maximum 4 pages:

Question n°	Common theme	Contrasting findings
1. What does civic engagement mean to you?	Most of the respondents believe that social involvement is nothing more than participating in social life, being part of it. It is also taking part in social campaigns, volunteering, selfless help and responsibility. They think it is important to protect their own opinion, help people and take part in elections.	Some of the respondents believe that it is nothing but paying taxes, being a model citizen. One of the respondents admits that so far he has not been interested in it, but thanks to the survey he will increase his knowledge about it.
2. Have you participated in any of these initiatives in the last two years?	Flashmob: 1 Awareness campaigns on social Networks: 5 Petition: 8 Square demonstrations, marches, sit-in: 6 None of these: 10	
3. What was the cause?	- I wanted to defend my rights (4) - Promotion of initiatives (2) - Environmental issues (4) - I was interested in the topic (2) - Equality march (1) - Defending a person (2)	No answer (16)

<p>3.</p> <p>Do you think that technology could play a role in promoting social inclusion and equal participation? If yes, how? If not, why not?</p>	<p>Most respondents admitted that the use of technology today is very positive and plays a very important role, especially among young people. They agreed that technology gives us a lot of possibilities, thanks to it we can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate with other people and organise various social events - Promote events - Protect the environment - Have better access to information - Sign petitions electronically - Create a group of people with similar views in social media 	<p>Two out of 31 respondents were not convinced by the new technology, they admitted that it can play an important role, but they are not entirely sure which one, they also point out that it depends on people.</p>
<p>4.</p> <p>Are you aware of game-based learning initiatives? If so, could you name these? what do you think?</p>	<p>The data collected from this survey shows that most of the respondents are familiar with game - based learning initiatives. Various games are given as examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Board games (Monopoly) - WINGS - Stratagame - SIMS (which teaches us how to manage money) - Educational applications such as Duolingo, Babble - Rubby Warrior - Codlin Game - Score hunter - Hotel Giant 	<p>14 out of 31 respondents have never heard of game-based learning initiatives.</p>

	Respondents think that this approach is very good, thanks to games we learn faster, because knowledge is given to us in a very attractive form, so we are able to remember more	
5. Do you know of any initiatives on young people's civic engagement you consider 'best practices'? If yes, name them.	22 out of 31 respondents admitted that they did not know any initiatives on young people's civic engagement.	People who have heard of such initiatives mention: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WOŚP - an annual event which involves thousands of people from all over Poland. Young people integrate and help others. I think it's a beautiful initiative because they collect money that they donate to hospitals later on. - Promotion on Facebook and Instagram, since more young people are using these social media channels in comparison to LinkedIn and Twitter, which are channels chosen more often by professionals. - Parliament of youth - IAMEUROPE - Europe for Citizens - Doctors without Borders - Szlachetna Paczka - Erasmus+
How do you think Gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young adult?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting civic activities alone is a good idea, through the game, young people can learn many things they had no idea about before - Through the game, the player can learn various concepts related to social engagement. He may be in contact with other people - By providing different scenarios and various 	Some of the respondents admit that gamification could be used to enhance critical reflection on social and political circumstances of young people but they're not sure how it can work.

	<p>solutions to these scenarios and feedback</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - it could be used in mobile apps, users could get fast information and support - learning by fun, using social media - communication with others 	
<p>According to you what are the most successful activities and practices for fostering civic participation, social inclusion and gender equality among young people (i.e. diversity-days with games, workshops, exhibitions, theatre, round-tables/debates, competitions on drawings, photographs, etc.)?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All those mentioned / combination of the activities mentioned in the question – most of the respondents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizenship project - anyone can submit a project regarding e.g. public space development or another project that everyone will be able to use and which will be financed by the state - ‘Personally for me the best methods are movies, short videos to aware us about importance of every different person and respect to each other whoever you are’ - Social media activities - Promoting gender equality in schools <p>Two of the respondents are not convinced of such initiatives, they believe that there is no chance to implement them in their community, and because of the prevailing pandemic it is not possible to implement them.</p>

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